

IMPLEMENTATION AND EFFICACY OF CONTINUOUS AND COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION WHILE EVALUATING CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

Dr. Poonam

Assistant Professor,
Maharaja Surajmal Institute.

Neha Gupta

M.A. Education, IGNOU.

Abstract:

The board (CBSE) introduced Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation scheme (CCE) to overcome the shortcomings of traditional examination system. According to CBSE, CCE refers to a system of school based evaluation of students that covers all aspects of students' development. CCE aims to evaluate every aspect of a child during her presence in school.

According to CBSE evaluation in inclusive education needs to be done with an Individual Evaluation Program. Specific goals should be set for each child with special need based upon the appraisal. The focus of the present research is to study the perceptions of the teachers teaching in schools of East Delhi with reference to the implementation and efficacy of CCE of Children with Special Needs (CWSN). The study revealed that the teachers agree that they have access to CBSE circulars, evaluation guidelines for CWSN. Schools have provision of counselor for CWSN.

Introduction:

A good evaluation and examination system can benefit both the learners and the educational system by giving credible feedback. Education is concerned with preparing citizens for a meaningful and productive life and evaluation should be a way of providing credible feedback on the extent to which we have been successful in imparting such an education. (NCERT, 2005)

CCE is the new evaluation method to decrease the accumulated stress of board exams on the students and to introduce a more uniform and comprehensive pattern in education. CCE scheme refers to a school-based evaluation of students that covers all the aspects i.e. scholastic and the co-scholastic aspects of a student's development. It is a curricular initiative, attempting to shift emphasis from testing to holistic learning. It aims at creating good citizens possessing sound health, appropriate skills and desirable qualities besides academic excellence.

CCE helps in improving student's performance by identifying her learning difficulties and abilities right from the beginning of the academic session and employing suitable remedial measures for enhancing their learning performance. This is believed to help reduce the pressure on the child during/before examinations.

Objectives:

To study the perceptions of the teachers teaching in schools of East Delhi with reference to the implementation and efficacy of CCE of CWSN.

Methodology: In the present study Descriptive Survey Method has been used.

Sample: The sample consisted of sixty teachers, six each from 5 government schools and 5 private schools of East Delhi Zone.

Tools: The data in this study was collected through a self made questionnaire.

Results and Discussion:

Table1: Perception of teachers teaching in schools of East Delhi with reference to the implementation and efficacy of CCE of CWSN.

S.No.	Items	Responses%		
		Disagree	Undecided	Agree
1	Preparation of different question paper for CWSN.	35	15	50
2	Different evaluation and assessment procedure for CWSN.	30	12	58
3	Schools allow scribe, ICT, Braille books for CWSN.	35	3	62
4	Provision of wheel chair, Braille books and assistive devices.	45	12	43
5	Availability of documents related to CWSN in library.	32	22	47
6	Access to CBSE circulars and evaluation guidelines	20	3	77
7	Improvement in scholastic and co- scholastic areas after implementation of CCE.	18	30	52
8	Benefit in assessment after the implementation of CCE.	17	18	65
9	Provision of counselor for CWSN.	20	8	72
10	Same curriculum for CWSN.	37	13	50
11	Only paper-pencil tests for assessing CWSN.	73	7	20

Fig. 1 To study the perceptions of the teachers teaching in schools of East Delhi with reference to the implementation and efficacy of CCE of CWSN.

Fig. 1 indicates that half of the teachers i.e.50% agree that there should be a different question paper for CWSN while the other 35% expressed their disagreement. However 15% of the teachers surveyed are uncertain on the issue. 58% of the respondents agree that there should be different evaluation and assessment procedure for CWSN. 30% disagree to it while other 12% are undecided on the issue.

A majority of teachers i.e. 62% agree that school allow scribe, ICT and use of Braille books for CWSN. A negligible 3% are undecided while 35% disagree to it.

To the question whether School provides wheel chair, Braille Books, grip pens and other assistive devices for CWSN it is observed that 43% teachers agree and 45% disagree.12% are undecided on the issue. The Rights of Persons with Disabilities bill, 2014 states that suitable modifications should be made in the curriculum and examination system to meet the needs of students with disabilities. Facility of scribe or amanuensis, books, other learning materials and appropriate assistive devices to be provided to students with benchmark disabilities free of cost up to the age of eighteen years and either free or at

affordable cost, thereafter. Thus from the present study it can be concluded that though schools allow assistance in the form of books or amanuensis they do not provide such assistance to CWSN. Schools must ensure the same.

Fig.1 shows that 47% teachers agree that their School library has important documents related to CWSN. While 32% disagree to this, 22% are undecided on the issue. Teachers should have access to all the bills and amendments which directly relate to CWSN so that they could apply the appropriate measures in teaching and assessment.

Unanimously 77% teachers agree that they have access to CBSE circulars, evaluation guidelines for CWSN. 52% teachers agree that CWSN are showing improvement in scholastic and co-scholastic areas after the implementation of CCE. 18% teachers disagree to it while other 30% are undecided on the issue. More than half of the teachers i.e. 65% agree that CWSN are benefitted in assessment after the implementation of CCE while 17% & 18% disagree and are undecided respectively.

A majority of 72% teachers agree that there is a provision of counselor for CWSN. 50% agree that same curriculum should be followed in the school for special children. 37% disagree while 13% are undecided on it. The study conducted by Meynert (2014) shows the respondent's positive attitude towards inclusive education but they express their fear that these children may not be able to cope up with general curriculum.

Fig.1 indicates that 73% teachers disagree that to assess CWSN only paper-pencil tests should be taken. There is a great awakening among teachers that assessment of CWSN should include methods other than paper-pencil tests. This may include oral responses instead of written. SSA has outlined some important techniques of evaluation of CWSN. Some of them are:

- Questions can be provided on the Tape recorders and students' responses can also be recorded.
- Child may be permitted to write his/her answers in computers.
- Wherever possible computers with talk software can also be used as an evaluation mode.
- Use of sign language for evaluation. (Evaluation techniques in SSA)

Major Findings:

- 62% agree that school allow scribe, ICT and use of Braille books for CWSN.
- 77% teachers agree that they have access to CBSE circulars, evaluation guidelines for CWSN.
- A majority of 72% teachers agree that there is a provision of counselor for CWSN.
- 73% teachers disagree that to assess CWSN only paper-pencil tests should be taken.

Conclusion:

The present study revealed that though schools allow scribe, ICT for CWSN but many of the schools do not provide the necessary aids and assistive like wheel chair, Braille books, etc. to the children with special needs. Schools should ensure that the libraries have documents for CWSN and teachers are updated about any changes/amendments done by the government. By doing so effective evaluation can be carried out.

Suggestions:

- Similar study can be done for different zone, different states.
- Teachers from Kendriya Vidyalayas, Navodaya Vidyalayas, Rajkiya Pratibha Vikas Vidyalayas and Army Public School can be taken for a similar study.

Bibliography:

- Evaluation techniques for CWSN in SSA. Retrieved on 26.12.15 from ssa.nic.in/inclusive-education/.../EVALUATION%20GUIDELINES.../file
- Meynert, M.J. (2014). *Inclusive Education And Perceptions Of Learning Facilitators Of Children With Special Needs In A School In Sweden*. Retrieved on 6.7.15 from

http://www.internationalsped.com/documents/INCLUSIVE%20EDUCATION%20AND%20PERCEPTIONS%20OF%20LEARNING%20FACILITATORS%20OF%20CHILDREN%20WITH%20SPECIAL%20NEEDS%20IN%20A%20SCHOOL%20IN%20SWEDEN_FORMATTED1.pdf

- NCERT.(2005). *National Curriculum Framework*. National Council of Educational Research and Training. New Delhi.
- Right to Persons with Disabilities Bill. (2014). Retrieved on 23.12.15 from www.prsindia.org/.../Person%20with%20Disabilities/The%20Right%20of...